

Sociodemographic Survey of Students at The University of Guayaquil

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this research is to analyze the socio-educational conditions of students at the University of Guayaquil and their relationship with academic performance and retention in higher education.

A descriptive, quantitative study was conducted through the application of a structured survey to 150 students from different faculties, using non-probabilistic convenience sampling. The instrument collected sociodemographic, economic and family data, housing conditions, access to basic services, dietary habits, transportation, employment status, and perception of risk of academic dropout. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Most participants were between 18 and 25 years old, lived in urban areas, and were economically dependent on their families. A significant proportion came from households with monthly incomes below USD 600, which limited their ability to cover education-related expenses. Despite this situation, most students had not applied for scholarships or financial aid. Approximately one third of the students reported having considered dropping out of university due to economic reasons, highlighting the direct influence of financial conditions on academic continuity.

Socioeconomic conditions are a determining factor in student retention and academic performance. The findings emphasize the need to strengthen institutional policies focused on financial support, comprehensive student welfare, and differentiated strategies for programs with high academic workload in order to reduce the risk of student dropout.

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INTRODUCTION

In the student life of the students at the Universidad de Guayaquil, different factors have an influence, such as their demographic, economic, social, and academic situation. All these factors need to be identified; therefore, in this research study, socio-educational surveys will be applied to understand the reality of the student environment surrounding each learner. In this sense, the survey becomes a fundamental tool for understanding the reality and the challenges students face during their academic training.

These variables, in addition to providing a detailed profile of the student body, allow higher education institutions to

develop strategies and policies that promote academic success and improve students' living conditions. (1)

The Ecuadorian educational environment is characterized by the social, cultural, and economic diversity of its student population. This diversity not only enriches the university experience but also introduces specific challenges related to equitable access to educational resources, academic performance, and student retention in the higher education system. In this context, the Universidad de Guayaquil, as one of the most representative institutions in the country, has considered it essential to carry out a socio-educational diagnosis to understand the characteristics of its students and the conditions under which they develop their university life.

This survey has been designed with the objective of collecting precise and up-to-date data on the demographic, social, and economic characteristics of the students of this university. The topics addressed include essential variables such as age, marital status, and ethnic background, as well as aspects related to housing, family composition, and access to basic services such as drinking water, electricity, and internet. In addition, the survey analyzes issues related to transportation, commuting times to the university, and the expenses associated with their academic training.

In particular, the study pays special attention to the economic conditions of students, evaluating factors such as household income, the availability of financial resources for their education, and their participation in the labor market. This last aspect is especially important in a country where the need to combine work and study has become a common reality for many young people. This economic analysis is essential to identify barriers that may limit educational continuity, such as insufficient access to scholarships, financial aid, or the need to temporarily drop out for financial reasons. (2)

Likewise, the questionnaire addresses aspects related to students' eating habits, housing conditions, and access to basic services. Although these factors are often considered secondary, they have a significant impact on students' quality of life and academic performance. The information obtained will make it possible to identify critical areas that require immediate attention and to design intervention programs aimed at improving the living conditions of the student community.

Another central aspect of the study is the analysis of students' family dynamics. This approach seeks to understand how family dynamics influence students' academic performance and what strategies could be implemented to support them in their transition to university and professional life.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Higher Education and Its Importance in Social and Economic Development

According to UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization), higher education is defined as the set of educational programs “that follow secondary education and are delivered by universities or other institutions authorized as higher education providers by the competent national authorities and/or recognized accreditation systems” (3)(4).

Higher education plays an essential role in a country's development, as it serves as a driver of social mobility, the reduction of inequalities, and the training of competent professionals who promote economic, social, and productive progress. In Ecuador, the educational system has undergone significant transformation since the enactment of the Ley Orgánica de Educación Superior (LOES) in 2010, with the aim of ensuring equal opportunities and universal access to higher

education. However, these advances face challenges such as student dropout and the difficulty students experience in sustaining themselves economically during their academic training (5). The factors analyzed in this research such as economic conditions, social environment, and demographic aspects directly influence students' academic progress. A strong relationship has been observed between the high incidence of these socioeconomic factors and university dropout, affecting not only the students' future but also the progress of the country, since each student who drops out represents a loss of talent and potential for innovation and social development. (6) Dropout resulting from socioeconomic factors can be considered the most relevant consequence of these conditions, as it directly affects academic performance and student life (5) (7)

One of the greatest challenges faced by university students in Ecuador is economic precariousness. Socio-educational surveys show that a large proportion of students come from families whose income is below the minimum wage, and almost all respondents study full time and depend entirely on their families' financial support. This limits their ability to cover essential expenses such as tuition, materials, transportation, and food. According to the Socio-educational Survey of Students at the Universidad de Guayaquil, 3.3% of students dropped out for economic reasons, highlighting the magnitude of the problem and its impact on academic retention (2) (7) (8)

The COVID-19 pandemic intensified these inequalities, increasing dropout rates due to the loss of family income, limited access to technological resources, and inadequate connectivity for virtual education. In highly demanding programs such as Medicine, these difficulties are compounded by the impossibility of working while studying, leading many students to leave university because they cannot financially sustain themselves. Programs such as Engineering and Architecture also face similar challenges, since in public universities students must assume the full cost of materials for coursework, models, prototypes, and projects, in addition to transportation, housing (for students from other regions), and food expenses. (8)

Various studies have identified economic, social, and institutional factors that directly affect student performance and retention. Personal factors also influence academic performance, including self-esteem, lack of concentration, academic stress, difficulty adapting to the environment, interpersonal relationships, and unmet expectations (9).

From a social perspective, family income level, employment status, limited family support, and access to basic services are key determinants of academic success. At the institutional level, the availability of scholarships, support programs, student-teacher relationships, physical infrastructure, technological resources, and educational quality are crucial for promoting retention in universities (1)(6).

The Ecuadorian State has implemented initiatives such as the Sistema Nacional de Nivelación y Admisión (SNNA) and increased investment in higher education, seeking to guarantee equal opportunities and improve student conditions. Nevertheless, significant inequalities persist, especially for students from rural and low-income backgrounds. Official data indicate that available scholarships and financial aid are insufficient to cover the basic needs of all vulnerable students (10).

Programs such as Medicine present specific challenges that further hinder student retention. Medical students face long academic schedules and a heavy study load that prevent them from combining work with education, unlike students in more flexible programs. This creates greater economic pressure in a context where state aid is not always sufficient. For this reason, students in these disciplines require differentiated strategies, such as specialized funding programs, full scholarships, and mental health support. (11)

In higher education, it is essential to implement teaching strategies that go beyond the development of disciplinary competencies and also expand students' future opportunities and projections. These strategies strengthen the quality of the educational process and prepare students more comprehensively to face the challenges and demands of their professional lives (7).

The concept of didactic strategies encompasses a set of methods, resources, and techniques characterized by their flexibility and adaptability within the teaching-learning process. Currently, these strategies have evolved in response to new student needs, especially in educational contexts increasingly mediated by information and communication technologies (ICT).

Learning strategies have fundamental characteristics, including flexibility since they adapt to diverse educational contexts; intentionality because they involve the conscious application of metacognitive knowledge; and motivation because they consider not only academic objectives but also the affective factors that influence learning.

PROCEDURE

The research procedure focused on the administration of the Socio-educational Survey to students at the University of Guayaquil, which served as the primary instrument for data collection. The survey was applied to students through both digital modalities and during in-person activities conducted at the university. This dual approach expanded participation coverage and facilitated students' access to the data collection instrument.

Prior to its administration, the survey was structured by considering relevant socio-educational variables, drawing on previous studies conducted at the University of Guayaquil. These earlier studies had demonstrated the appropriateness of this type of instrument for characterizing the student population. The combined use of digital platforms and physical

spaces contributed to a more efficient and representative data collection process, ensuring the gathering of diverse and up-to-date information.

Throughout the survey administration, student participation was voluntary, and the confidentiality of the collected information was guaranteed. The data were used exclusively for academic and scientific purposes. This procedure adhered to widely accepted ethical standards in socio-educational research, thereby enhancing the study's reliability.

Once data collection was completed, the obtained information was reviewed, cleaned, and systematically organized. Subsequently, the data were entered into matrices for analysis, enabling the generation of results that reflect the current socio-educational reality of University of Guayaquil students. These findings can be compared with previous research conducted at the institution, which has reported relevant figures for both the university and society at large, thereby strengthening the validity of the present study.

PARTICIPANTS

The study sample consisted of a total of 150 students enrolled in different faculties of the Universidad de Guayaquil. Participants were selected from among students who were actively enrolled during the data collection period, which ensured that the information obtained reflected the institution's current academic reality.

The inclusion criteria focused on students who were enrolled in academic programs at the university at the time the survey was administered, ensuring diverse representation in terms of age, gender, socioeconomic status, and fields of study. This diversity within the sample made it possible to obtain a broad view of the students' socio-educational context, in accordance with the objectives established in the Socio-educational Survey of Students at the Universidad de Guayaquil.

Exclusion criteria were also established to ensure the reliability of the results. In this regard, students who had previously completed the questionnaire were excluded, thus avoiding duplicate responses that could affect the validity of the analysis. The application of these criteria strengthened the quality of the collected information and ensured that the analyzed data accurately reflect the characteristics of the participating student population

DATA ANALYSIS

The analysis of the data obtained from the Socio-educational Survey of Students at the Universidad de Guayaquil was carried out using descriptive statistics, with the aim of organizing, summarizing, and interpreting the information collected from the 150 participating students. This type of analysis made it possible to identify general characteristics and trends related to the socio-educational conditions of the student population.

The collected data were systematized in information matrices, which facilitated their processing and analysis. Frequencies

“Sociodemographic Survey of Students at The University of Guayaquil”

and percentages were used for the interpretation of the results, allowing a clear visualization of the analyzed variables, such as age, gender, socioeconomic status, and academic programs. This procedure is widely used in socio-educational studies and has proven to be appropriate for the characterization of university populations.

Likewise, the results obtained from the survey analysis were compared with findings reported in previous research conducted at the Universidad de Guayaquil, which present relevant figures for both the institution and society. This comparison strengthened the validity of the data, demonstrating that the information generated through the survey constitutes a significant contribution to understanding the socio-educational reality of the students.

In addition, the descriptive analysis of the data made it possible to generate useful information for interpreting the student context and for formulating academic and institutional strategies aimed at improving teaching-learning processes and student well-being. In this way, data analysis is consolidated as a key element for decision-making within the field of higher education.

RESULTS

The present study has a total population of 150 students from various faculties of the University of Guayaquil, whose sociodemographic characteristics are shown in Table 1.

Variable	Categorías	Porcentaje
Edad	Menores de 18 años	6%
	Entre 18 y 25 años	88.7%
	Entre 26 y 30 años	5.3%
	Mayores de 30 años	6%
Estado civil	Soltero/a	88.7%
	Otros (Casado/a, Divorciado/a, Unión, etc.)	11.3%
Grupo étnico	Mestizo	80%
	Otros (Indígena, Negra, Blanco, etc.)	20%
Residencia principal	Zona urbana	85.3%
	Zona rural o suburbana	14.7%
Acceso a internet	Con conexión estable	90%
	Con conexión limitada	8.7%
	Sin acceso	1.3%
Condición de vivienda	Propia (totalmente pagada o en proceso)	57%
	Arrendada	35.3%
	Prestada o cedida	8%
Ingresos del hogar	Menos del salario básico (\$470)	18.7%
	Entre \$470 y \$600	10%
	Entre \$601 y \$1,000	14.7%
	Entre \$1,000 y \$1,500	30%
	Más de \$1,500	26.7%
Situación laboral	Trabajo a tiempo completo	18.7%
	Trabajo a medio tiempo	2.6%
	No trabajan	78.7%

The table shows that the majority of respondents are between 18 and 25 years old (88.7%) and are single (88.7%), which is consistent with the predominant age range. Eighty percent identify as mestizo, and 85.3% reside in urban areas. Ninety percent have stable internet access, while regarding housing conditions, 57% live in their own properties. Income is mainly concentrated between \$1,000 and \$1,500 (30%), and 78.7% are not employed, suggesting economic dependence. Each variable will be analyzed individually in detail to further examine its relevance within the study.

Question 1

The results of the survey administered to 150 students show that 89% of respondents are between 18 and 25 years old, making this the predominant age range, which reflects that the majority belong to the typical profile of young students in higher education. To a lesser extent, 6% are between 26 and 30 years old, followed by 3% who are under 18 years old, and finally 2% who are over 30 years old.

These data highlight that the student population is largely composed of young adults, with low representation from other age groups. This may help guide the project's strategies and approaches toward the main characteristics and needs of this majority group.

Question 2

According to the survey results, 88.7% of the 150 participants indicated that they are single, making this the predominant marital status among respondents. To a lesser extent, 5.3% reported being married, followed by 4% who are in a common-law union. Meanwhile, the marital statuses of divorced, cohabiting, and in a relationship, each represent 0.7% of the responses.

These data show that the majority of respondents are single, reflecting a characteristic profile of young students. This may be a relevant factor in interpreting their needs and main concerns that could influence their academic life.

Question 3

As shown in Graph 3, 83% of respondents identify as belonging to the mestizo ethnic group. Three percent identify as Black,

“Sociodemographic Survey of Students at The University of Guayaquil”

2.7% as Indigenous, and a minority of 1.3% belong to the mulatto ethnic group.

These data reflect ethnic diversity, although with a marked predominance of mestizo identity. This may be relevant for designing inclusive strategies that take into account the cultural and social particularities of each group within the project.

Question 4

The information obtained from Question 4 reveals that 55% of respondents graduated from public (state) institutions, making this the most representative type of institution. To a lesser extent, 21% come from semi-private institutions, 16% from municipal institutions, and 8% from academies.

These data show diversity in the types of institutions of origin, with a predominance of public institutions. This may be a relevant factor in understanding the participants' previous educational context and in adjusting the project's strategies according to these characteristics.

Question 5

The results of Question 5 show that the majority of respondents, 68%, are studying Medicine, making it the predominant degree program. Other programs with significant representation are Law (6%), Nursing (5%), and Obstetrics (5%). Psychology and Industrial Engineering each account for 2% of respondents.

Additionally, 1% of respondents study Economics, Graphic Design, Nutrition and Dietetics, or Occupational Therapy, while 0.7% belong to programs such as Architecture, Auditing and Management Control, Foreign Trade, Gastronomy, Geological Engineering, Information Technology Engineering,

Project Management, Experimental Sciences Education – Informatics, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), or Tourism.

These data reflect a predominant focus on health-related programs, which may guide the project's design toward the needs and characteristics of this majority group.

Question 6

Out of the total 150 students, 40.7% are enrolled in upper-level semesters (fifth semester and above). To a lesser extent, 36.7% are in the fourth semester, while 10% are in the first semester. Additionally, 7.3% are in the second semester, and 5.3% are in the third semester, as shown in Graph 6.

Question 7

According to the results regarding the number of people respondents live with, 57% live with between 3 and 5 members of their household, representing a typical family structure. Meanwhile, 16.7% live with fewer than 3 people, reflecting smaller households, and 16% live with between 6 and 8 people, indicating larger families.

Additionally, 6% reported living alone, showing a smaller proportion of independent individuals, and 4.7% stated that they live with more than 8 people, possibly in extended or multigenerational households, as shown in Graph 7.

Question 8

Out of the total 150 students, it was identified that the predominant construction material used in housing is cement, accounting for 84%, indicating that most homes are built with durable and commonly used material. Six percent of the homes are constructed with concrete, an equally solid alternative, while 6.7% are built with bricks, reflecting another common construction option.

Meanwhile, 1.3% of the homes are made of wood, suggesting a lower presence of less durable materials. Additionally, 0.7% are built with bahareque (cane, mud, or wood coated with mud or cement), 0.7% with a combination of cement and wood, and the remaining 0.7% with adobe—traditional materials that represent a small proportion, as shown in Graph 8.

Question 9

Among the respondents’ places of residence, the urban area predominates with 85.3%, while 10.7% live in rural areas and 4% reside in suburban areas, as shown in Graph 9.

This reflects a marked concentration of respondents in urban areas, probably due to greater educational opportunities and access to services. Meanwhile, a minority live in rural or suburban areas, which could influence their conditions of access and the resources available to them.

Question 10

Regarding internet access, 90% of respondents indicated that they have a stable connection. Meanwhile, 8.7% have limited access, and 1.3% do not have internet access, as shown in Graph 10.

This demonstrates that the vast majority have adequate service for their needs. However, a small proportion still face limitations or lack access in this regard, which could represent a barrier to activities related to education or work.

Question 11

The results obtained from the survey allow us to infer that the majority of respondents have an adequate diet. Graph 11 shows that 91.3% of respondents eat lunch daily, making it the most frequent meal.

Secondly, 86.7% reported that they regularly eat dinner, while 65.3% stated that they have breakfast every day. However, 21.3% indicated that they have additional meals, such as mid-morning and/or mid-afternoon snacks.

These data reflect the predominant dietary patterns among the surveyed students.

Question 12

Based on the results of the survey conducted, it was identified that 32% of respondents take between 16 and 30 minutes to arrive, making this the most frequent option. Secondly, 28.7% reported a commuting time of 31 to 60 minutes, while 22% indicated that they take 15 minutes or less.

Meanwhile, 8% of students stated that their travel time ranges between 61 and 90 minutes, 6.7% mentioned that they take between 91 and 120 minutes, and 2.7% reported that their commuting time exceeds 120 minutes. Although these latter percentages represent a smaller proportion of the surveyed population, they highlight the existence of a group of students who face prolonged travel times, which could influence their level of fatigue, time availability, and academic performance.

Question 13

The study shows that the most frequent option is the bus (public or university transportation), used by 52% of respondents. Secondly, 16% of students indicated that they walk to the university, followed by 12.7% who use their own vehicle. Meanwhile, 8.7% of respondents stated that they use taxi services (Uber, Cabify, Yellow, or cooperative) for transportation, while 6% use a car or motorcycle belonging to a friend or family member. Additionally, 4% reported traveling by interprovincial bus, and 0.7% commute by bicycle. These data reflect that the majority of students rely on public transportation to reach the university, while a smaller proportion use private or alternative means such as bicycles or walking.

Question 14

Based on the results of the survey conducted, the most frequent option is living in a fully paid, owner-occupied home, reported by 35.3% of respondents. Secondly, 30.7% of students indicated that they live in rented housing, while 18.7% reside in a home that is owned and was donated, inherited, or acquired through possession.

Meanwhile, 8% of respondents mentioned that they are currently paying for their home, and 6.7% indicated that their housing is loaned or provided free of charge. Finally, 0.7% of students stated that they live in a home owned by their uncles. These data show that the majority of surveyed students live in owner-occupied housing, whether fully paid or acquired through inheritance or donation, while a considerable proportion depends on rental housing.

Question 15

Based on the results of the survey conducted, the most common services among respondents are electricity, present in 99.3% of households, and drinking water, with a coverage rate of 98.7%. Likewise, 98% of respondents indicated that they have internet access at home, while 89.3% have access to a sewage system. On the other hand, the service with the lowest coverage is garbage collection, available in 84.7% of households. These data show that the vast majority of respondents have access to essential services such as electricity, drinking water, and internet, while a smaller percentage face limitations in the availability of sewage systems and waste collection services.

Question 16

According to the results obtained from the survey regarding Question 16 (“What is the average income among all household members?”), 30% of the surveyed students indicated that their total household income ranges between \$601 and \$1,000. Meanwhile, 26.7% reported income between \$470 and \$600. However, 18.7% mentioned that their total household income is below the minimum wage (\$470), while 14.7% stated that their household earns between \$1,000 and \$1,500. Finally, 10% indicated that their total household income exceeds \$1,500.

Question 17

According to the results obtained from the survey regarding Question 17 (“Do you receive any economic income?”):

- 66% of students indicated that their income comes exclusively from their parents or relatives.
- 12.7% stated that they earn income independently through their own work.
- 10.7% mentioned that they receive income both from family members and from their work.
- 10.7% indicated that they do not receive any type of income.

The 10,7% who do not receive income from any source may include students facing significant financial difficulties, as they lack both family support and personal earnings. This group is particularly vulnerable to issues such as university dropout, debt, or the need to apply for scholarships and financial aid in order to continue their studies.

The results of these questions are complemented by others such as “Have you applied for a scholarship or financial aid?” and “Have you ever withdrawn or considered withdrawing from your studies for economic reasons?”, since it is likely that a large proportion of students who depend exclusively on their families or who have no income have considered these options in order to continue their academic training.

Students who rely exclusively on their families may face greater difficulties in covering tuition costs, materials, transportation, and other essential expenses, which may affect their educational quality and emotional well-being.

Question 18

According to the results obtained from Question 18 (“Have you applied for a scholarship or financial aid?”):

- 86% of students have not applied for any scholarship or financial aid.
- 7.3% applied for a scholarship or aid but did not receive it.
- 6.7% applied and did receive it.

The most significant finding is that the vast majority of students (86%) have not applied for any scholarship or financial aid, which is concerning considering that, in Question 16, it was shown that a significant proportion of households have low incomes (45.4% earn less than \$600). This suggests that a considerable percentage of students who could benefit from a scholarship have not attempted to access this type of support.

Question 19

Regarding the employment status of students, the results show that the majority are not currently employed, representing 78.7% of the sample. Additionally, 18.7% of respondents work part-time, while only 2.7% reported having full-time employment.

These results illustrate the distribution of students’ employment status at the time the survey was administered.

Question 20

The results regarding Question 20 (“¿What are your average monthly educational expenses?” (tuition, materials, transportation, etc.) indicate the following:

- 41.3% of students spend between \$100 and \$200 per month on their studies.
- 26% spend less than \$100 per month.
- Another 26% have monthly expenses ranging between \$200 and \$400.
- 6.7% of respondents report expenses exceeding \$400.

The most representative group is the 41.3% who spend between \$100 and \$200 per month, suggesting that although university tuition may be relatively affordable, other costs such as materials, transportation, and food create a significant financial burden for students.

It is relevant to compare these data with the results of Question 16 (average household income), where 30% of households earn between \$601 and \$1,000, and 26.7% between \$470 and \$600. This implies that, for a considerable proportion of students, educational expenses represent a substantial share of the family income, which could lead to financial difficulties, especially if the household has more than one student.

Question 21

The results corresponding to the question about the possibility of having withdrawn or considered withdrawing from their studies for economic reasons show that the majority of students have not contemplated this option, representing 65.3% of respondents.

However, a significant percentage, equivalent to 31.3%, indicated that at some point they considered withdrawing from the university due to financial difficulties, although they ultimately did not carry out that decision. Meanwhile, 3.3% of students reported that they actually withdrew from the university for economic reasons.

These results reflect the distribution of students’ experiences regarding the impact of their financial situation on the continuity of their studies.

RESULTS ANALYSIS

The overall analysis of the results reveals that the surveyed students exhibited social, educational, and economic characteristics that directly influence their university experience. Demographically, this is a young population, predominantly single and aged between 18 and 25 years, a profile considered typical of higher education students. Notably, the majority belong to the mestizo ethnic group, reflecting the general demographic composition of the university environment under consideration.

Regarding family structure and housing, most students live in medium-sized families, primarily with 3 to 5 members. This suggests potential economic pressure when contrasted with reported household incomes. Although the majority reside in homes constructed with good-quality materials and located in favorable, predominantly urban areas, quality of life is not uniformly high, particularly for those sharing limited financial resources among multiple family members.

Access to basic services yields largely positive results, with high availability of potable water, electricity, and internet. However, a portion of students experiences limited internet access, which may represent a disadvantage for academic activities, especially in contexts where virtual platforms and digital materials are essential to the learning process.

With respect to dietary habits, the findings indicate that lunch and dinner are the most consistent main meals, whereas

breakfast tends to be more irregular. This pattern may be linked to economic constraints and/or demanding academic schedules, potentially compromising students' health, energy levels, and academic performance. The limited consumption of mid-morning or mid-afternoon snacks further underscores the need to promote healthier eating habits among university students.

In terms of student mobility, a substantial proportion relies on public transportation as the primary means of commuting to the university, consistent with reported income levels. While most experience moderate travel times, a significant number endure long commutes, which can lead to fatigue, reduced study time, and heightened academic stress, ultimately affecting performance.

From an economic perspective, the results show that a relevant number of students come from low- and middle-income families, often centered around the basic salary level. This situation is exacerbated by high economic dependence on families, as most students lack personal income and exhibit very low employment rates. Although this dependency may allow greater focus on studies, it also renders students more economically vulnerable if family resources are insufficient to cover educational or personal expenses.

A key finding is the low uptake of scholarships or financial aid, despite a notable proportion of students facing unfavorable economic conditions. This pattern may stem from limited awareness of available programs, bureaucratic barriers, or unclear information regarding eligibility requirements. The limited access to scholarships highlights the need to strengthen institutional strategies for dissemination, guidance, and support in application processes. Particular attention should be given to question 21 (intention to drop out due to economic reasons), as students encountering financial difficulties without employment or aid may be forced to interrupt their studies.

The analysis of economic variables and academic persistence indicates that, while most students have not considered withdrawing, a sector has contemplated it due to economic pressures. Monthly educational expenses, combined with the absence of personal income or institutional support, constitute a risk factor for academic continuity.

Collectively, these findings demonstrate that economic conditions, lifestyle habits, and access to resources are determinant factors in students' university experience. Therefore, there is a clear need to implement institutional policies that enhance scholarship access, improve the dissemination of financial aid opportunities, and foster conditions conducive to overall well-being and academic persistence.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study was conducted in accordance with internationally recognized ethical principles for research in the social and health sciences. Participation was entirely voluntary, without

coercion, undue incentives, or academic consequences associated with the decision to participate or decline.

Before completing the questionnaire, participants received clear and comprehensive information regarding the objectives, scope, and purpose of the study. Given the anonymous and non-invasive nature of the instrument, informed consent was considered implicitly granted upon voluntary completion of the survey.

Anonymity and confidentiality were strictly maintained. No personal identifiers were collected, and no information allowing direct or indirect identification of participants was obtained. Data were used exclusively for academic and scientific purposes and were analyzed in aggregated form. All information was handled responsibly to preserve participants' privacy and ensure data protection.

The principles of beneficence and non-maleficence were upheld throughout the research process. The study posed no physical, psychological, or social risks to participants. The findings are intended to contribute to the understanding of students' socioeducational conditions and to support the development of institutional strategies aimed at improving student well-being and retention in higher education.

All data were managed with scientific integrity and transparency. The results will not be used for discriminatory or commercial purposes.

DISCUSSION

The findings indicate that economic, social, and familial factors significantly influence academic performance and retention among students at the University of Guayaquil. A substantial proportion of participants reported limited household income, consistent with previous research conducted in Ecuadorian public universities, where socioeconomic status has been identified as a major determinant of student dropout. (12)

The high level of financial dependence on family support, combined with a low rate of student employment, reflects financial vulnerability. Although most students do not work, this may be attributable to the demanding academic workload, particularly in health-related programs such as Medicine, which require near-exclusive dedication. This condition limits opportunities for independent income generation and increases reliance on family resources that may be insufficient to meet educational expenses.

Despite evident financial need, a low proportion of students reported applying for scholarships or financial aid. Possible explanations include limited awareness of available programs, perceived administrative barriers, or misconceptions regarding eligibility criteria. Strengthening institutional dissemination and support mechanisms may improve access to financial assistance.

Educational expenses, including indirect costs such as transportation, academic materials, and food, represent a significant financial burden. Nearly one-third of students reported having considered discontinuing their studies for

economic reasons, and a smaller proportion reported having interrupted their academic training. These findings underscore the role of financial constraints as a critical factor in university retention.

Although most students reported access to basic services and internet connectivity, disparities persist that may affect academic performance, particularly in virtual or hybrid learning contexts. Additionally, dietary habits and commuting time—often overlooked variables—may influence students’ physical and mental well-being, indirectly affecting academic outcomes.

These findings support the need for comprehensive institutional policies that address not only academic performance but also socioeconomic and well-being factors. Targeted strategies for academically demanding programs, combined with financial, psychological, and academic support services, may contribute to reducing dropout rates and promoting equity in higher education.

CONCLUSION

The results of the present study conducted at the University of Guayaquil demonstrate that the economic, social, and family conditions of students are key determinants both in their academic performance and in their permanence in higher education, a finding that coincides with research carried out in Ecuadorian public universities(9)(12). The diversity of students and inequalities in access to resources are persistent challenges that require urgent attention from academic authorities. Although government policies, such as scholarships and financial aid, have attempted to mitigate some of these barriers, evidence suggests that significant gaps still exist that negatively affect students' training and well-being (13).

Likewise, it was evidenced that, despite the existence of scholarship programs and financial aid, most students do not access these benefits. This situation has previously been described as a structural limitation of the higher education system in Ecuador, where financial support coverage is insufficient compared to student demand(12). This finding acquires special relevance when considering that nearly one third of the students reported having considered dropping out of their studies for economic reasons, which is consistent with studies that identify economic factors as one of the main causes of university dropout(4).

On the other hand, the analysis shows that socioeducational inequalities do not affect all degree programs in the same way. Programs with high academic and time workload, such as Medicine and other careers in the health area, present greater difficulties in balancing study, work, and personal well-being, increasing the economic and emotional pressure on students(13)(10).

Overall, the findings highlight the need for higher education institutions to adopt a comprehensive approach that is not limited only to academic quality, but that also incorporates policies aimed at the social, economic, and emotional well-

being of students. Systematically addressing socioeducational inequalities will help reduce student dropout, strengthen educational equity, and contribute to the social and economic development of the country, in accordance with the principles established by UNESCO on the strategic role of higher education(7).

RECOMMENDATIONS

Expansion of scholarships and financial aid: It is recommended to increase the budget allocated to scholarships and financial aid, especially for students from low-income households. Evidence indicates that timely financial support significantly reduces the risk of dropout and improves academic continuity(9)(12). These aids should cover not only academic costs, but also expenses associated with transportation, food, and study materials.

Psychological support and well-being programs: Given the impact that economic difficulties have on the emotional and academic well-being of students, a psychological support system should be established with programs that promote mental health, especially for students who face greater challenges in their daily lives. Various studies have shown that personal and social factors, such as stress, anxiety, and maladjustment to the university environment, negatively influence academic performance (14).

Flexibility of schedules and study modalities: For students who combine work and studies, flexibility in schedules and the offer of study modalities that allow balance between both activities are recommended. This includes the option of virtual or hybrid classes, as well as the consideration of more flexible schedules for those who have long working hours. This strategy has been identified as an effective measure to promote student retention without compromising educational quality(11).

Strengthening technological infrastructure and connectivity: The pandemic highlighted the need to improve access to technological tools and connectivity for virtual education. It is recommended that the university invest in technological infrastructure, offering devices and free or affordable access to students who do not have these resources. UNESCO highlights that access to educational technologies is a key component in reducing gaps in higher education(5).

Academic orientation and support programs: It is crucial to create programs that help students in their transition to university, providing guidance on time management, study techniques, and integration into university life. These programs should also address the importance of physical and emotional health, to provide resources on how to face academic challenges.

Differentiated policies for high-demand careers: It is essential that universities develop differentiated policies for students in careers with high academic workload, such as Medicine, Obstetrics, Biochemistry, Engineering, who face greater economic and logistical challenges. These policies should include specialized scholarships, sustained financial

support, and psychological support, as indicated by studies on academic performance in health-related careers(15).

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